

6GSMART-SP1-L1-P1-D2.1
Revisión del estado del arte y diseño
inicial de la integración público-privada
en 6GSMART
v1.0

Fecha de Publicación: 25/07/2023

[Nombre Sub-Proyecto]
6GSMART-ICC

Programa de Universalización de
Infraestructuras Digitales para la Cohesión –
6G I+D

Paquete de Trabajo (PT)	6GSMART-SP1-L1-P2
Líder del PT	TID/Minsait
Editor Principal	Jose Manuel Palacios (Minsait)
Contribuyentes	Jose Antonio Ordoñez-Lucena (TID)
Nivel de diseminación	PU
Tipo	RE

Nivel de diseminación

PU	Publico
PP	Restringido a otros participantes del programa
RE	Restringido a un grupo especificado por el consorcio
CO	Confidencial solo para miembros del consorcio

Tipo

PR	Prototipo
RE	Reporte
SP	Especificación
TO	Herramienta
OT	Otro

Histórico de versiones del documento				
versión	Autor	Estado	Fecha	Comentarios
0.1	Jose Antonio Ordoñez-Lucena	Draft	14/06/2023	High Level ToC Proposal
0.2	Jose Antonio Ordoñez-Lucena	Draft	30/06/2023	Content for Chapters 7.1, 7.3, 8.2 and 9.1
0.3	Jose Manuel Palacios	Draft	07/07/2023	Content for Chapters 8.3 and 9.2
0.4	Estela Carmona	Draft	19/07/2023	General Revision
0.5	Jose Manuel Palacios	Draft	20/07/2023	Fix revision comments
1.0	Jose Manuel Palacios	Final TID/Minsait	25/07/2023	Final TID/Minsait review

1 Table of Contents

1	Table of Contents	3
2	List of Tables	4
3	List of Figures	5
4	List of Acronyms	6
5	Executive Summary	8
6	Introduction	8
7	Public-private (hybrid) networks in industrial environments	9
7.1	Industry 4.0 ecosystem	9
7.1.1	Use cases	9
7.1.2	Technology enablers	12
7.2	Public-private network integration [ATOS]	16
7.3	Network-as-a-Service	16
8	Technical Innovations	19
8.1	Seamless inter-domain resource orchestration in public-private network scenarios [ATOS]	19
8.1.1	State of the art	20
8.1.2	Innovation in 6GSMART-ICC	20
8.2	NaaS ecosystem in manufacturing market segment	20
8.2.1	State of the art	20
8.2.2	Innovation in 6GSMART-ICC	23
8.3	Capability exposure between different administrative domains	25
8.3.1	State of the art	25
8.3.2	Innovation in 6GSMART-ICC	34
9	Preliminary System Architecture	36
9.1	System Requirements [TID, MINSAIT, ATOS]	36
9.2	High-Level Design [TID, MINSAIT, ATOS]	37
10	Summary and conclusions	39

2 List of Tables

Table 1: Application areas and use cases in the industry 4.0 ecosystem. Source: 3GPP TR 28.804.	10
Table 2: Industry 4.0 example use cases. Source: 5G-ACIA.	11
Table 3: TSN standardization landscape.	13
Table 4: Industrial edge flavors and features.....	15
Table 5: Telco capabilities for OT industry consumption.....	21
Table 6: 3GPP APIs useful for capability exposure in industry 4.0 ecosystem.....	23
Table 7 Capabilities consumed by CSC for each level	26
Table 8 5G-CLARITY Management Models	28

3 List of Figures

Figure 1: Overview of selected industry 4.0 use cases, arranged according to their 5G service requirements. Source: 5G-ACIA.	10
Figure 2: Edge computing concept. Source: [34]	14
Figure 3: Industrial edge computing concept. Source 5G-ACIA 16	15
Figure 4:NaaS ecosystem – roles and usage of APIs	17
Figure 5: PNI-NPN scenarios. Source: 5G-PPP.....	19
Figure 6: capability exposure in industry 4.0. Source: 5G-ACIA 21.....	21
Figure 7: 3GPP exposure solutions for Industry 4.0.....	22
Figure 8 5G-VINNI exposure levels.....	26
Figure 9 Multi-domain solution based on 5Growth.....	27
Figure 10 3GPP CAPIF framework	31
Figure 11 CAPIF Generic workflow for service API invocation	32
Figure 12 Red Hat 3scale architecture	33
Figure 13 Solution Architecture.....	38
Figure 14 GSAM Open Gateway.....	39

4 List of Acronyms

3GPP	3rd Generation Partnership Project
5G-ACIA	5G Alliance for Connected Industries and Automation
AEF	API Exposure Function
AI/ML	Artificial Intelligence / Machine Learning
AMF	API Management Function
APF	API Publishing Function
API	Application Programming Interface
BSS	Business Support System
CAPIF	Common API Framework
CCF	CAPIF Core Function
CI/CD	Continuous Integration Continuous Delivery
CN	Core Network
CSC	Communication Service Consumer
CSMF	Communication Service Management Function
CSMF-C	Communication Service Management Function Consumer
CSP	Communication Service Provider
DS-TT	Device-Side TSN Translator
eMBB	Enhanced Mobile Broadband
E2E	End to End
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
GPSI	Generic Public Subscription Identifier
GSM	Global System for Mobile communications
GSMA	GSM Association
HMI	Human Machine Interfaces
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
IIoT	Industrial IoT
IoT	Internet of Things
IT	Information Technology
LAN	Local Area Network
MaaS	Monitoring as a Service
MEC	Mobile Edge Core
MF	Management Function
mIoT	Massive IoT
MNO	Mobile Network Operator
MWCB22	Mobile World Congress Barcelona 22
NaaS	Network as a Service
NEF	Network Exposure Function
NFV	Network Function Virtualization
NFVO	Network Function Virtualization Orchestrator
NOP	Network Operator
NPN	Non-Public Network
NRM	Network Resource Management
NS	Network Service
NSD	Network Service Descriptor
NSI	Network Slice Instance
NSMF	Network Slice Management Function
NW-TT	Network-Side TSN Translator
OAM	Operation Administration and Management
OSS	Operations Support System

OT	Operational Technology
OTT	Over The Top
PLMN	Public Land Mobile Network
PN	Public Network
PNF	Physical Network Function
PNFD	Physical Network Function Descriptor
PNI-NPN	Public Network-Integrated NPN
QoD	Quality on Demand
QoS	Quality of Service
RAN	Radio Access Network
REST	Representational State Transfer
SCEF	Service Capability Exposure Function
SDN	Software Defined Network
SEAL	Service Enabler Architecture Layer for Verticals
SLS	Service Level Specification
SNPN	Standalone Non-Public Network
SOAP	Simple Object Access Protocol
TaaS	Testing as a Service
TN	Transport Network
TSN	Time-Sensitive Networking
UPF	User Plane Function
URLLC	Ultra-Reliable Low-Latency Communication
VAE	Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) Application Enabler
VIM	Virtual Infrastructure Manager
VNF	Virtual Network Function
VNFD	Virtual Network Function Descriptor
WAN	Wide Area Network
WIM	WAN Infrastructure Manager
XML	eXtensible Markup Language

5 Executive Summary

Enablers such as 5G are allowing the industry to have greater flexibility in connectivity services. 5G-ACIA is promoting the installation of 5G private networks with both stand-alone models and models with integration of public-private networks.

Edge computing and 5G service/connectivity provisioning capabilities (e.g., slicing) are not considered within the 5G-ACIA exposure landscape. However, these capabilities are presumed to play a key role for industry 4.0 service innovation and new business models. 6G-SMART-ICC aims to define which capabilities related to edge computing and 5G service/connectivity provisioning make sense to expose to industrial applications, and push these capabilities for their adoption into GSMA Open Gateway initiative, to promote their adoption at large scale.

On the other hand, current APIs to expose network capabilities (NaaS) to industrial applications are studied. Organizations such as 3GPP and CAMARA have defined Capability Exposure APIs. 3GPP exposure APIs cannot be directly exposed to industrial applications, since their semantics convey low-level parameters that are quite complex for OT companies to understand (and thus configure/monitor). And CAMARA seems a more appropriate target, though today's focus is on mass-market, whose SLS expectations are quite far from the ones inherent to industry 4.0 services. 6G-SMART-ICC is going to identify which CAMARA APIs can remain valid for industry 4.0 services, and how they need to be enriched to cope with the specificities of these services.

Finally, the exposure of capabilities between different domains is studied with special emphasis on the API Gateway, reaching the conclusion that the OT enterprise needs to be provided with a single-entry point to manage service, even for the cases where the service resources spanned across the IoT-edge-cloud continuum, with different provider domains in between. This has an impact on the discovery of resources, and their programmatic consumption through APIs, in a consistent way.

6G-SMART-ICC aims to bridge this gap, by crafting a mediation solution that provides OT enterprises with consistent yet resilient access to service capabilities in distributed environments.

6 Introduction

This document reviews the state of the art of the mechanisms for integrating public and private networks under development by the 3GPP and 5G-ACIA communities. Based on this review, as part of this activity, the design principles to follow for the 6GSMART public-private interconnection system will be identified.

The document is organized in five main chapters:

- Chapter 5: Executive Summary
- Chapter 7: Includes a review on industry 4.0 ecosystem, public-private network integration and Network-as-a-Service.
- Chapter 8: Technical innovations on:
 - Seamless inter-domain resource orchestration in public-private network scenarios

- NaaS ecosystem in manufacturing market segment
- Capability exposure between different administrative domains
- Chapter 9: Includes system requirements and high-level system design
- Chapter 10: Summary and conclusions.

7 Public-private (hybrid) networks in industrial environments

7.1 Industry 4.0 ecosystem

Currently, the manufacturing sector is undergoing a fundamental transformation known as the "industry 4.0"¹. Industry 4.0 describes the "fourth industrial revolution", which aims at transforming today's factories into intelligently connected production information systems that operate well beyond the physical boundaries of the factory premises. The main goals of Industry 4.0 are to enhance worker support, flexibility, adaptability, resource efficiency, cost efficiency, worker support, and the standard of industrial production and logistics. Factories of the future leverage the smart integration of "cyber-physical-systems" and Internet of Things (IoT) solutions in industrial processes².

The deliverable 6GSMART P2-P1-D1.1 reported on some market insights on industry 4.0 sector. In deliverable 6GSMART P2-P1-D2.1, the focus will be on use cases and technology enablers.

7.1.1 Use cases

As of today, the 5G Alliance for Connected Industries (5G-ACIA) is the main driver for the development of private 5G solutions in industry 4.0 ecosystem. With a consortium formed of telco players, Operation Technology (OT) stakeholders and regulators, 5G-ACIA's main mission is to work towards the vision of the factories of the future³ based on fully connected 5G factories for smart manufacturing and logistics services.

5G-ACIA has defined a number of use case families for industry 4.0, which are reported in these papers⁴. As seen in Table 1, these families can be allocated to the following application domains: i) factory automation, ii) process automation, iii) HMI and production IT, iv) logistics and warehousing, and v) monitoring and maintenance.

¹ X M. Wollschlaeger, T. Sauter, and J. Jasperneite, "The Future of Industrial Communication: Automation Networks in the Era of IoT and Industry 4.0", *IEEE Industrial Electronics Magazine*, pp. 17-27, 2017

² S. K. Rao and R. Prasad, "Impact of 5G Technologies on Industry 4.0", *Wireless Personal Communications*, vol. 100, no. 1, pp. 1-15, 2018

³ 5G-ACIA, "5G Alliance for Connected Industries and Automation", 2019 [Online]. [Link](#)

⁴ 5G-ACIA, "5G for Connected Industries and Automation", White Paper, Feb 2019 [Online].

[Link](#)

5G-ACIA, "5G for Automation in Industry", White Paper, July 2019 [Online]. [Link](#)

5G-ACIA, "5G Non-Public Networks for Industrial Scenarios", White Paper July 2019 [Online].

[Link](#)

5G-ACIA, "A 5G Traffic Model for Industrial Use Cases", White Paper, November 2019 [Online].

[Link](#)

Table 1: Application areas and use cases in the industry 4.0 ecosystem. Source: 3GPP TR 28.804⁵.

Use case families	Factory automation	Process Automation	HMIs and Production IT	Logistics and Warehousing	Monitoring and Maintenance
Motion control	X				
Control-to-control				X	
Mobile control panels with safety functions			X		
Remote access and maintenance		X		X	
Augmented reality					X
Closed-loop process control		X	X		
Process monitoring		X			
Plant asset management		X		X	

Figure 1: Overview of selected industry 4.0 use cases, arranged according to their 5G service requirements. Source: 5G-ACIA⁶.

⁵ 3GPP TR 22.804, "Study on Communication for Automation in Vertical domains (CAV)"

⁶ 5G-ACIA, "Service-Level Specifications (SLS) for 5G Technology-Enabled Connected Industries", 2022 [Online]. [Link](#)

These use cases have different service requirements. Figure 1 shows this casuistry, but positioning these use cases along the 5G space. Table 2 selects a subset of these use cases, and reports on their service level specification (SLS). The requirements highlighted for this SLS characterization include availability, cycle time (space between transmission in periodic communications), typical payload sizes, number of devices (scalability) and coverage.

Table 2: Industry 4.0 example use cases. Source: 5G-ACIA⁷.

Use case family	Use Cases	Availability	Cycle Time	Typical payload size	N. of devices	Coverage
Motion control	Printing machine	>99.9999%	< 2 ms	20 bytes	>100	100m x 100m x 30m
	Machine tool	>99.9999%	< 0.5 ms	50 bytes	~20	15m x 15m x 3m
	Packaging machine	>99.9999%	< 1 ms	40 bytes	~50	10m x 5m x 3m
Mobile robots	Cooperative motion control	>99.9999%	1 ms	40-250 bytes	100	< 1 km ²
	Video-operated remote control	>99.9999%	10-100 ms	15.150 kbytes	100	< 1 km ²
Mobile control panels with safety functions	Assembly robots or milling machines	>99.9999%	4-8 ms	40-250 bytes	4	10m x 10m
	Mobile cranes	>99.9999%	12 ms	40-250 bytes	2	40m x 60m
Process automation	Process monitoring	>99.99%	> 50ms	Varies	10000 devices per km ²	

For this use case taxonomy and profiling, 5G-ACIA took inputs from:

- 5G-PPP white paper⁸ on Factories of the Future, released in 2015. This document provides the EU view with regards to the digitalization of manufacturing and logistics industries, based on the insights resulting from 5G-PPP Phase I projects.
- Third Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) SA1, which has supported factory and process automation⁹ by collecting a wide range of use cases related to cyber-

⁷ 5G-ACIA, "5G for Connected Industries and Automation", White Paper, Feb 2019 [Online]. [Link](#)

⁸ 5G-PPP, "5G and the Factories of the Future", White Paper, 2015 [Online]. Link: <https://5g-ppp.eu/wp-content/uploads/2014/02/5G-PPP-White-Paper-on-Factories-of-the-Future-Vertical-Sector.pdf>

⁹ 3GPP TS 22.104, "Service requirements for cyber-physical control applications in vertical domains"
3GPP TS 22.261, "Service requirements for the 5G system; Stage 1"

physical applications and normative end-to-end service and network performance requirements.

- Global Mobile Suppliers Association (GSA), which proposed a three-level model spanning performance, functional and operational requirements¹⁰. Functional requirements have to do with network capabilities (e.g., positioning, device management) that OT partners can use. Operational requirements refer to the system's ability to manage and run communication services, such as QoS monitoring and reporting.

7.1.2 Technology enablers

This section summarizes the technology enablers unleashing industry 4.0 ecosystem. These include: (i) 5G; (ii) Wi-Fi; (iii) TSN and (iv) edge computing.

Enabler #1: 5G

The 5G represents a set of capabilities that allows providing mobile network services for wireless connectivity. The first release standardization body responsible for the specification and maintenance of these capabilities is 3GPP. Though the first 3GPP release for 5G was Rel-15, the starting point for private 5G was Rel-16, later enhanced with Rel-17. The launch of Rel-18 kicked off the 5G Advanced era, also known to as Beyond 5G (B5G). At the time of writing of this deliverable, Rel-18 is about to close, with first Rel-19 work planned to get started in 2024. For further details on 3GPP 5G releases, see¹¹.

From Rel-16 on, the 3GPP 5G system¹² has been provided with a number of capabilities that have contributed to enrich the industry 4.0 ecosystem with new service innovation levers. These capabilities include:

- **Network slicing:** is a cutting-edge solution that aims at splitting the infrastructure into a set of logical network partitions, each optimized (in terms of capacity, topology functions, configuration and management) to satisfy a particular set of services.
- **5G Local Area Networks:** It allows realizing the grouping and connection between designated 5G devices, facilitating enterprises to build a more mobile LAN network. This grouping results into the allocation of devices into 5G Virtual Networks (5G-VNs), each supporting layer-2 and layer-3 communication and x-cast communications.
- **Positioning:** encompasses the collection, processing, and management of device-centric data to provide location services.
- **Clock synchronization:** it represents the ability to synchronize a device's time clock to a clock and support a mechanism to process and transmit related time synchronization protocols for 3rd party applications which use those protocols.
- **Messaging services:** used for providing one to one, group and broadcast message services with low end-to-end latency and high reliability of message delivery, in a resource efficient manner to optimize the resource usage in the network, and power saving in the user devices.

¹⁰ GSA white paper, "5G Network Slicing for Vertical Industries", Sept 2017

¹¹ Qualcomm white paper, "Setting off the 5G Advanced evolution", January 2022 [Online]. [Link](#)

¹² 3GPP TS 23.501, "5G; System Architecture for the 5G System (5GS)"

Enabler #2: Wi-Fi

Wi-Fi is an IEEE 802 technology, which has been widely used as a preferable access technology in private LTE and factory networks. Wi-Fi deployment is fast, easy, and cheap compared to private cellular networks, making it an attractive choice where speed and economy are a priority. Private Wi-Fi networks are already used in factories, typically for non-critical applications.

Many industry reports have focused over the last two years on making comparative analysis between industrial Wi-Fi, private 5G, capturing their pros and cons in terms of performance and cost. Examples of these analysis can be found in these papers¹³. The results show that it is not an either-or situation; at the end of the day, the reality is that private 5G will continue to coexist with Wi-Fi. The focus should now be put on understanding where and when each connectivity solution is best suited, finding potential network synergies and taking advantage of any opportunity for consolidation. With the sight set on meeting this goal, 5G-CLARITY project¹⁴ has developed solutions that showcase the frictionless integration of 5G and Wi-Fi technologies, and their combined use to achieving higher throughput and improved reliability in private networks.

Enabler #3: TSN

TSN is a set of standards specified by IEEE 802 to enable Ethernet networks to give QoS guarantees for time-sensitive and/or mission-critical traffic and applications. Unlike 5G or Wi-Fi, which aim at providing wireless connectivity, TSN focus is wired connectivity. The various TSN standards provide differing QoS guarantees. Table 3 captures the most relevant ones, identifying their scope and area of actuation.

Table 3: TSN standardization landscape.

QoS aspect	Feature	IEEE references
Bounded low latency	Frame preemption	802.3br, 802.1 Qbu
	Time Scheduling	802.1Qbv
	Cyclic Queuing and Forwarding	802.1Qch
	Asynchronous Traffic Shaping	802.1Qcr
Reliability	Frame Replication and Elimination	802.1CB
	Path Control and Reservation	802.1Qca
Resource management	Stream Reservation Protocol	802.1Qat
	Credit Based Shaper	802.1Qav
	Per-Stream Filtering and Policing	802.1Qci
Synchronization	Periodic and deterministic networking	802.1AS

¹³ M. Bamforth, "Private 5G vs Wi-Fi vs Private LTE", STL Partners, 2021 [Online]. [Link](#)
M. Addicks, "Private 5G vs Wi-Fi: The New Wave of Wide-Area LAN", September 2021 [Online]. [Link](#)

¹⁴ H2020 5G-CLARITY project [Online]. [Link](#)

TSN can be used together with 5G. For further details on how this integration looks like, see¹⁵.

Enabler #4: edge computing

Edge computing represents a paradigm whereby data storage and processing takes place in a location as close as possible to the user, device or service that will consume/produce the data. In a nutshell, it can be seen as the result of having a cloud continuum along the entire infrastructure, from end device up to the internet. Figure 2 illustrates this continuum, where the concept of “telco edge” is present at different locations, typically within the boundary of operator networks (see “far edge” and “near edge”), but also beyond them (see “on-premises” edge). In the latter case, edge computing is placed at customer premises, for example within factory buildings or inside transportation hubs. The reasons for having on-premises workloads typically respond to security concerns and/or policy regulations (e.g., data residency), and for some very specific use cases, to achieve ms-level latencies.

Figure 2: Edge computing concept. Source: GSMA¹⁶

5G-ACIA has released a white paper on industrial edge computing¹⁷. This document examines how edge computing features of 5G network can improve IIoT use cases, concluding that they deliver many other benefits besides improved latency, including enhanced aggregation capabilities as well as greater resiliency and reliability. It also proposes different flavors picturing the realization industrial edge computing concept: “single OT production domain”, “multiple OT production domain” and “outside enterprise premise (but nearby)”. This proposal is represented in Figure 3. It is worth noting that the 5G-ACIA assumes edge computing platform (hosting OT application and its runtime

¹⁵ 5G-ACIA, “Integration of 5G with Time-Sensitive Networking for Industrial Communication”, 2021 [Online]. [Link](#)

¹⁶ GSMA, “Telco Edge Cloud Value & Achievements”, 2022 [Online]. [Link](#)

¹⁷ 5G-ACIA, “Industrial Edge Computing - Use Cases, Architecture and Deployment”, 2020 [Online]. [Link](#)

environment) is co-located with UPF. Although this configuration is not mandatory, it is very likely choice for many practical deployments.

Figure 3: Industrial edge computing concept. Source 5G-ACIA 17

Table 4 provides a characterization of these three flavors.

Table 4: Industrial edge flavors and features.

Flavor	Edge node location	Requirements	In-scope use cases
Single OT production domain	OT production domain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Latency-sensitive High reliability and availability Data must be entirely stored locally Devices inside one single OT domain 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Closed-loop control Mobile robots Evolved collaborative robots

Multiple OT production domain	IT Enterprise domain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Latency-sensitive • High reliability and availability • Data must be entirely stored locally • Devices inside multiple OT domains 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mobile robots (with mobility among OT production domains) • Evolved collaborative robots (with mobility among OT production domains) • Remote access and maintenance (data needs to be stored locally) • Video surveillance service (data needs to be stored locally)
Outside enterprise premise	MNO core network local site (e.g., central office)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Latency-tolerant • High reliability and availability • No need to store all data locally. • Mobility among remote locations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Remote access and maintenance • Video surveillance service • Mobile positioning and asset tracking

7.2 Public-private network integration [ATOS]

<Revision of the concept of public-private integration and its challenges and the state of the art regarding the deployment of E2E applications inter-domain>

7.3 Network-as-a-Service

Network-as-a-Service (NaaS) represents a paradigm shift whereby network operators can make telco capabilities from public networks available for external consumption, including monitoring and configuration related capabilities, through Application Programming Interface (APIs). These APIs paves the way for transforming telco networks into programmable service platforms that can be easily accessed by 3rd parties, including application developers, application service providers, ISVs, and enterprise customers.

According to the description noted above, NaaS enables these 3rd parties to integrate their applications into network, with open and direct interactions between them. This releases them from the constraints of traditional over-the-top, best-effort service delivery models, tapping into newly exposed capabilities to provide enhanced user experience and contribute to the digital ecosystem with new services.

The development of NaaS requires a collaborative workspace that bring together incumbent telco standard bodies with IT/cloud communities, industry associations and open-source projects. An effective collaboration among organizations needs to be based on a clear demarcation on their scope of work, avoiding their participating organizations running overlapping activities or duplicate efforts; otherwise, NaaS may risk ending up with a fragmented ecosystem. To that end, GSMA launched Open Gateway in MWC Barcelona 23. GSMA Open Gateway mission is twofold: i) to provide a governance

framework for NaaS, covering technical and business aspects; ii) to get operator commitment to launch universal NaaS API services in 2023.

Open Gateway initiative recognizes that NaaS the concept builds on the work developed by three organizations:

- **Linux Foundation’s CAMARA:** it represents the “exposure” doctrine, i.e., how capabilities are exposed for external consumption through 3rd party facing APIs. CAMARA defines these APIs and is responsible for their hosting and release management. 3rd party facing APIs are user-friendly (semantics tailored to service and business needs of 3rd parties) and open (following Apache2.0 license).
- **GSMA:** it represents i) the “technical” doctrine, by specifying how 3rd party facing APIs are to be supported by underlying telco capabilities, including network and cloud capabilities; and ii) the “business” doctrine, with the definition of agreement templates for federation between the operator networks and for relationship with 3rd parties, ensuring a consistent yet fair commercial framework for exposing services. GSMA conducts the technical workstream through OPG/OPAG (Operator Platform Group / Operator Platform API Group) and the business workstream through WAS (Wholesale Agreement Services) group.
- **TM Forum:** it represents the “operational” doctrine, i.e., how 3rd party facing APIs are to be operated and managed, to make a commercial product out of them. Representing the IT side of operators, that includes Operation, Administration and Maintenance (OAM) functionality provided by OSS and BSS, and on-line charging systems, now structured following a new digital architecture referred to as Open Digital Architecture (ODA).

Figure 4 illustrates the contributions of these organizations into the Open Gateway actor-role model.

Figure 4:NaaS ecosystem – roles and usage of APIs

On the one hand, the scope of **GSMA** is circumscribed to the telco domain. GSMA prescribes the capabilities that all operators must make available for 3rd parties, to ensure

global reach and scale. These must-be capabilities are referred to as Open Gateway services. The GSMA is also responsible for i) the prioritization and roadmap management of Open Gateway services, according to market needs and commercial readiness of underlying technologies; and ii) architecting the platform that individual operators will use to realize¹⁸, and expose¹⁹ Open Gateway services.

On the other hand, the scope of **CAMARA** and **TM Forum** is on the APIs that allows programmatic access to Open Gateway services. As seen in Figure 4., these APIs can be clustered into three groups:

- Service APIs: they allow invoking Open Gateway services. Examples of these APIs are Quality on Demand API, Device Location API, Device Status API, SIM Swap API, OTP validation API or Carrier Billing API. As noted, these APIs provide purpose-specific application-tailored functionality.
- Service Management APIs: they allow running certain management actions from within Open Gateway services, like ordering the activation/de-activation of certain functionality for that service, monitoring, eligibility check or consumption check.
- Operate APIs: they provide all the transversal (non-service specific) functionality that is required to make a commercial product out of the Open Gateway services, making them operable and monetizable. Examples of OAM functionality provided by the Operate APIs include registration/onboarding of 3rd parties, service fulfilment (e.g., provisioning, activation, and modification), service assurance (e.g., incident management, service supervision and performance) and billing.

With regards to API owners, Service and Service management APIs are defined, developed, tested, and maintained by CAMARA, while TM Forum is responsible for Operate APIs.

With regards to targeted consumers, it is worth noting that CAMARA APIs are used by application developers (green line in Figure 4). These APIs are delivered through aggregators (wholesale model), or by the telco itself using its portal (retail model). The aggregators may develop and expose additional “Enriched APIs” (yellow line), by adapting or combining CAMARA APIs. The Operate APIs (red line) are not used by application developers, but for integration with aggregators and portals instead. Further details on CAMARA APIs can be found in the White Paper published in²⁰.

In the context of 6G-SMART-ICC, public-private network integration can rely on GSMA Open Gateway initiative as follows:

- MNOs represent the public network segment. They offer i) advanced 5G connectivity services, e.g., slicing; and ii) programmatic access to telco capabilities.
- OT enterprises represent the private network segment. They assume the role of application developer and application service provider, owning the industrial application and i) get it deployed when and where needed, ii) configuring to consume telco network capabilities.

¹⁸ For the realization, the NaaS platform needs to gain access to operator internal capabilities, including cloud and network resources. To that end, a Southbound Interface (SBI) is needed.

¹⁹ For the exposure, the NaaS platform makes use of Northbound Interface (NBI).

²⁰ GSMA, Linux Foundation and TM Forum White Paper, “The Ecosystem for Open Gateway NaaS API Development”, 2023 [Online]. [Link](#)

The integration of industrial applications and public network resources as noted above, together with the allocation of their workloads (e.g., application backend, 5G Advanced Core Functions, 5G Advanced virtual RAN) along the cloud continuum pictured in Figure 2 produced a number of Public Network Integrated Non-Public Networks (PNI-NPNs) scenarios. Examples of these scenarios are pictured in Figure 5.

Figure 5: PNI-NPN scenarios. Source: 5G-PPP²¹.

8 Technical Innovations

8.1 Seamless inter-domain resource orchestration in public-private network scenarios [ATOS]

²¹ 5G-PPP White Paper, “Non-Public Networks – State of the art and way forward”, November 2022. [Online]. [Link](#)

8.1.1 State of the art

<Pre-6G project>

8.1.2 Innovation in 6GSMART-ICC

8.2 NaaS ecosystem in manufacturing market segment

8.2.1 State of the art

In Section 7, we have analyzed industry 4.0 (Section 7.1) and NaaS ecosystem (Section 7.2) separately; it is time to converge both worlds. To that end, we need to consider the vision from both the OT industry (led by 5G-ACIA) and telco industry (led by 3GPP).

5G-ACIA vision

The 5G-ACIA collected and documented the requirements on 5G exposure capabilities for process automation, production IT, logistics and warehousing industry verticals, and published them in a white paper²². Figure 6 depicts the 5G-ACIA vision on capability exposure. This vision builds on the definition of three exposure reference points for an industrial application to gain access to telco capabilities. These reference points are: “**Ed**”, which allows interfacing with individual devices; “**En**”, which is the entry point to the infrastructure network, and “**Nm**”, used to consume network management and configuration services available in the Network Operation Center (NOC). From the figure, one can note that “Ed” is accessible for client-side application (in-device app), while “En” and “Nm” are available for server-side application (backend application).

²² 5G-ACIA, “Exposure of 5G Capabilities for Connected Industries and Automation Applications”, 2022. [Link](#)

Figure 6: capability exposure in industry 4.0. Source: 5G-ACIA 22

From the standpoint of backend application (located in IT enterprise domain), exposed capabilities can be grouped into two major families:

1. Device management, with focus on use cases related to the management of communication services for devices.
2. Network management, in particular operations and maintenance tasks for the 5G private networks, i.e., NPNs.

Further details on these capabilities and applicable 5G-ACIA reference points can be seen in the table below.

Table 5: Telco capabilities for OT industry consumption.

Family	Capabilities	Exposure interfaces
Device Management (section 4.2 from 22)	Device identity management	Ed
	Device provisioning and onboarding	Nm
	Device connectivity management	En
	Device connectivity monitoring	En
	Device group management	Ed, En
	Device location	Ed, En
Network Management (section 4.3 from 22)	Network monitoring	En
	Network configuration and maintenance	Nm

3GPP vision

3GPP has developed standard solutions to address the exposure-related requirements of the verticals by offering integration points between their systems and the 5G network.

These solutions hide the complexity of 5G and offer industry verticals a simple, secure, use-case-oriented configuration interface to the 5G system. The exposure interfaces will be invaluable to a multitude of industrial use cases, allowing industry verticals to make use of the key features and performance that 5G has to offer in a simple and straightforward manner.

Figure 7 provides an overview of 3GPP standards that are applicable for industry 4.0 use cases. From the bottom to the top, the following three layers of 3GPP exposure are depicted: i) the network exposure layer; ii) the service enabler architecture layer; and iii) the vertical application enabler layer. A comprehensive overview of these layers is reported in this paper²³.

Figure 7: 3GPP exposure solutions for Industry 4.0.

The **network exposure layer** consists of the 5G Network Exposure Function (NEF)²⁴, which offers network capabilities exposure of the 5G Core toward external applications integrated with the 3GPP network.

The **service exposure architecture layer (SEAL)** exposes common service enablers for verticals. Because the NEF APIs expose network capabilities in a highly granular manner, verticals using them must have a good understanding of the underlying network concepts. To simplify application development and deployment, 3GPP has specified a new layer of simplified service enablers. The SEAL²⁵ consists of service enablers that provide services that are not specific to any vertical – that is, they are common services that applications can utilize from various vertical domains.

Finally, there is the 3GPP **vertical application enabler (VAE) layer**, which exposes vertical-specific service enablers. In contrast to the SEAL, the VAE layer is tailored to

²³ D. Fragkos, G. Makropoulos, P. Sarantos, H. Koumaras, A. -S. Charismiadis and D. Tsoikas, "5G Vertical Application Enablers Implementation Challenges and Perspectives," 2021 IEEE International Mediterranean Conference on Communications and Networking (MeditCom), Athens, Greece, 2021, pp. 117-122, doi: 10.1109/MeditCom49071.2021.9647460

²⁴ 3GPP TS 29.522, "5G; 5G System; Network Exposure Function Northbound APIs; Stage 3"

²⁵ 3GPP TS 23.434, "Service Enabler Architecture Layer for Verticals (SEAL); Functional architecture and information flows"

service specific vertical applications. As of today, the verticals service enablers are defined for i) automotive applications referred to as vehicle-to-anything (V2X) communication, ii) drone applications known as unmanned aerial systems (UAS), and iii) OT applications, also referred to as factories of the future (FF). For further information on FF application layer capabilities, see²⁶.

Table 6 summarizes the 3GPP APIs that are relevant for industry 4.0 use cases in scope of 6G-SMART ICC.

Table 6: 3GPP APIs useful for capability exposure in industry 4.0 ecosystem.

Exposure layer	APIs
NEF 24	Event monitoring (device location, reachability, connection status)
	Application session with QoS (on-demand QoS for IP and Ethernet connections)
	Analytics exposure (with optional NWDAF processing)
	5G LAN parameter provisioning (device group management)
	Service parameters provisioning (policy and URSP provisioning)
	Time synchronous exposure
SEAL 25	Group management
	Location management
	Identity and key management
	Network Resource Management (NRM), including i) unicast/multicast scenarios management; ii) event monitoring; and iii) deterministic device-to-device and device-to-enterprise network communication
	Network slice capability enablement
VAE-FF 26	To be defined (as reported in SA#100, June 2023).

8.2.2 Innovation in 6GSMART-ICC

From the literature review conducted in the previous section, one can easily notice two open questions:

- Q1: Which telco capabilities makes more sense to expose to industrial applications?
- Q2: As for the APIs used to expose the capabilities identified in Q1, how should API style and semantics be/look like?

5G-ACIA vision on capability exposure is a good starting point to answer Q1. When mapping this vision into the NaaS framework conceptualized by GSMA Open Gateway, it can be noted that:

²⁶ 3GPP TS 23.545, "Application layer support for Factories of the Future (FF)"

- The “Ed” reference point is out of scope of Open Gateway. The reason is that this reference point refers to frontend application, while the notion of 3rd party application in Open Gateway is limited to backend applications.
- The “En” reference point correspond to the NaaS platform’s NBI delivering “Service” and “Service Management APIs”, i.e. CAMARA APIs. These APIs are available for consumption to 3rd party applications.
- The “Nm” reference point corresponds to the NaaS platform’s NBI delivering “Operate APIs”, i.e., TM Forum APIs. These APIs are not available for consumption to 3rd party applications, but to aggregators/portals instead.

In the context of 6G-SMART-ICC, where 3rd party application corresponds to an industrial application, only the capabilities exposed through “En” reference point would apply. Having a look at Table 5, one can notice that only three 5G-ACIA defined exposure capabilities match this criteria: i) device connectivity management, ii) device connectivity monitoring, and iii) network monitoring.

Gap: Edge computing and 5G service/connectivity provisioning capabilities (e.g., slicing) are not considered within the 5G-ACIA exposure landscape. However, these capabilities are presumed to play a key role for industry 4.0 service innovation and new business models, as reported in Section 7.1.

Action plan: 6G-SMART-ICC aims to bridge this gap identified for Q1, by:

- defining which capabilities related to edge computing and 5G service/connectivity provisioning makes sense to expose to industrial applications.
- pushing these capabilities for their adoption into GSMA Open Gateway initiative, to promote their adoption at large scale.

As for the Q2, the 3GPP exposure landscape picture in Figure 7 constitutes a solid foundation. The functional blocks (NEF, SEAL and VAE) and their APIs (reported in Table 6) provide solutions that support 5G-ACIA expectations with regards to capability exposure. Despite this alignment, it is worth noting that these solutions exhibit some limitations. In particular:

- The semantics of NEAL and SEAL APIs convey low-level parameters that are quite difficult for industry 4.0 verticals (in their role of app developers and application service providers) to interpret in their backend systems.
- VAE is a solution with very low traction in the market, and with no support (as of today) from main operators.

Linux’s Foundation CAMARA (see Figure 4) was launched precisely to solve these limitations. CAMARA has become the reference initiative with regards to defining APIs for 3rd parties with low telco background/expertise, as it happens with OT enterprises. Apart from being subjected to Apache 2.0 license, which facilitates their adoption at wide scale, CAMARA APIs abstracts telco APIs into something much more user-friendly, tailored to the business and operational needs of 3rd parties. The main problem is that, as of today, CAMARA APIs are much oriented for mass-market; however, the OT industry is a very specific market segment, with capabilities that are quite specific in terms of functionality, scalability (no need to accommodate a large of number of users) and performance (focus on very low-latency and very-high reliability).

Gaps:

- 3GPP exposure APIs cannot be directly exposed to industrial applications, since their semantics convey low-level parameters that are quite complex for OT companies to understand (and thus configure/monitor).
- CAMARA seems a more appropriate target, though today's focus is on mass-market, whose SLS expectations are quite far from the ones inherent to industry 4.0 services.

Action plan: 6G-SMART-ICC aims to bridge these gaps identified for Q2, by identifying which CAMARA APIs can remain valid for industry 4.0 services, and how they need to be enriched to cope with the specificities of these services.

8.3 Capability exposure between different administrative domains

8.3.1 State of the art

Capability exposure between different administrative domains has been addressed in several projects founded by the European Union. As the most relevant projects in this field, we can highlight 5G-VINNI, 5GROWTH, 5G-CLARITY and HEXA-X.

5G-VINNI

5G-VINNI²⁷ project aims to accelerate the uptake of 5G in Europe by providing a highly advanced end-to-end facility to validate the performance of new 5G technologies. Researchers will test network visualization techniques and advanced network architectures such as 5G network slicing as a service.

5G-VINNI uses the ecosystem of services defined by 3GPP (see 3GPP TS 28.530) to offer its customers (5G-VINNI customer) the services provided by each provider (5G-VINNI facility). Four levels of service exposure have been defined: Level 1, Level 2, Level 3 and Level 4 as depicted in Figure 8

²⁷ <https://www.5g-vinni.eu/>

Source: 5G-VINNI

Figure 8 5G-VINNI exposure levels

Table 7 summarizes the operational capabilities a CSC can get from the 5G-VINNI facility depending on selected exposure level.

Table 7 Capabilities consumed by CSC for each level

Exposed capability	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4
Service application layer configuration and management operations	✓	✓	✓	✓
SC application layer configuration and management operations (3GPP scope for RAN and CN, and IETF/BBF scope for TN)	✗	✓	✓	✓
SC management operations at the virtual resource layer, including operations related to VNF/NFV-NS lifecycle, performance and fault management (NFV scope)	✗	✗	✓	✓
Resource control and management operations at the infrastructure layer, including (i) VDU/VM lifecycle management, (ii) considerations on Enhanced Platform Awareness capabilities, and (iii) assistance for SDN control	✗	✗	✗	✓

5GROWTH

5Growth²⁸ is an AI-driven automated 5G E2E service platform that integrates 5G connectivity with network slicing, virtualization and multi-domain solutions. Custom network slices are instantiated to concurrently support the service requirements of multiple, heterogeneous applications over a shared network infrastructure that not only comprises different types of resources (e.g., at the edge, cloud, and transport) but also spans across multiple administrative domains (e.g., PNI-NPN scenario).

²⁸ <https://5growth.eu/>

Multi-domain support

As described in this paper²⁹, a multi-domain solution is proposed on top of the 5Growth platform for the integration of a NPN with PLMNs, motivated by the business needs of different verticals and by new or extended roles of different stakeholders as depicted in Figure 9.

Source: IEEE Access

Figure 9 Multi-domain solution based on 5Growth

The proposed solution address three different levels of multi-domain interaction, including: (i) Communication Service Level; (ii) Network Slice Level; and (iii) Network Service Level, as shown in Figure 9.

Communication Service Level.

A communication service, or more in general a vertical service, can be deployed across multiple domains. In this case, the vertical service is composed of elements that can be considered as sub-services, possible to be instantiated in domains controlled by different CSPs. The provisioning of this kind of service needs to be coordinated across multiple target domains in order to deliver the whole E2E.

Network Slice Level

In this scenario, the CSMF-C needs to identify the network slices associated to the vertical sub-services whose resources must be allocated into the external domain and to request their instantiation to the NSMF located there. The interaction between the two domains becomes a hierarchical one (the green straight line in Figure 9) and the CSMF-C acts as client for both the local and the remote NSMFs.

²⁹ https://e-archivo.uc3m.es/bitstream/handle/10016/33975/Multi-domain_IEEEA_2021.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y

Network service level

The NFV Network Service (NFV-NS) decomposition allows creating a single Network Slice that spans across different domains, provided that a suitable interconnection between all ends of the slice is established. This corresponds to the orange dotted line in Figure 9. In this case, the NSMF of the client side composes the E2E network slice as multiple NFV-NSs and requests their deployment to multiple NFVOs belonging to different NOP domains.

5G-CLARITY

5G-CLARITY³⁰ implements an SDN/NFV platform that is composed of a Management and Orchestration stratum and an Intelligence stratum.

The Management and Orchestration stratum has a functional group called The External Access Mediation. This group is in charge of exposing Network Capacities to other entities, such as the intelligence stratum or an external OSS, e.g., belonging to a mobile network operator (MNO).

5G-CLARITY ecosystem opens doors to a great variety of service delivery models, which go well beyond 3GPP scope: WAT as a Service (WATaaS), NFV Infrastructure as a Service (NFVlaaS) and Slice as a Service (SlaaS). For example, the WATaaS model is an adaptation of the existing neutral hosting model, whereas the NFVlaaS model is used to make a virtual infrastructure available for VNF/VAF hosting. Finally, the SlaaS model is about making a 5G-CLARITY slice (i.e. on-premise infrastructure slice) available for a 5G-CLARITY tenant, so it can consume in their own administrative domain as desired.

To make services available for customer consumption, the above service delivery models leverages on the capability exposure. Capability exposure is organized in Management Models that allow different exposure levels and interactions between actors from public and private domains. This definition is made under two assumptions. One is that higher exposure levels mean more advanced management capabilities. The other statement is that the management capabilities exposed by a certain level also contains those capabilities offered by the lower levels.

Table 8 describes Management Models supported by 5G-CLARITY

Table 8 5G-CLARITY Management Models

Service	Related Service Delivery Model	Mgmt.Level	Description
5G-CLARITY Wireless Service	WATaaS	WAT.MM1	Tenant: manages FCAPS (streaming telemetry and data lake access) and the lifecycle of network slices (S-NSSAIs).
5G-CLARITY Compute Service	NFVlaaS	NFVI.MM1	Tenant: provides VNFDs/NSDs and software images for Application Functions (AFs) and manages FCAPS (streaming telemetry and data lake access)

³⁰ <https://www.5gclarity.com/>

		NFVI.MM2	Tenant: NFVI.MM1 + management of lifecycle of VNFs/NSs (deploy, scale, heal, operate -start/stop/restart/...- , update and terminate, policies, etc.), onboarding of VNFDs/NSDs for NFs and AFs. The tenant connects to the private operator's NFVO to manage all the features aforementioned.
		NFVI.MM3	Tenant: NFVI.MM2 + connection to SP's VIM through its own NFVO in order to have increased capability to manage VNF/NS lifecycle.
5G-CLARITY Network Slice	SlaaS	SL.MM1	Tenant: supports the deployment of AFs, including WAT.MM1 (S-NSSAI LCM) + NFVI.MM1 (VNFDs/NSDs)
		SL.MM2	Tenant: manages the lifecycle of a 5G-CLARITY Slice, including WAT.MM1 + NFVI.MM2 (VNF/NS LCM).
		SL.MM3	Tenant: it includes WAT.MM1 (S-NSSAI LCM) + NFVI.MM32 (connection to VIM).

Hexa-X

Hexa-X project includes a block called API Management Exposure that enables communication among the different M&O resources, within and across administrative domains, enabling the so-called capability exposure of network elements in the different architectural layers.

In a multi-domain and federated scenario, resources and functions belonging to multiple administrative domains can also cooperate consuming APIs exposed by external domains. As consequence, a common and unified framework regulating the exposure and the management of the various APIs provided by different domains is required. Here, different levels of access and granularity should be supported for the various M&O resources, depending on the profile of the entity that invokes their API. Moreover, the dynamic nature of the environment, where new resources and functions can be added and removed at runtime, brings requirements for the dynamic discovery of the available APIs, and the level of exposure provided for the different categories of potential internal or external consumers.

This framework can exploit the concepts introduced by the CAPIF (Common API Framework), defined in the 3GPP TS 23.222 specification. The M&O functions that expose APIs for potential consumers need to register and de-register their APIs, providing enough details to describe the different levels of exposure towards a variety of invokers. For example, for a slice management function, the list of slices may be available in read-mode for both internal and external entities, while the possibility to create new slices may be restricted to other functions of the same domains. Similarly, the possibility to request the modification of an existing slice may be available only for the entity that initially created it or an internal function of the slice itself, for example, an AI/ML component.

In order to support an effective cooperation among different actors, the framework should also allow third-party entities to register their own functions and APIs, in order to make them available in a dynamic manner. In addition, APIs should be deployed utilizing an integration or CI/CD pipeline (from the Design Layer) to enable multiple advantages as, automated staging, testing and version management of the APIs, effortless new API management, and fast and reliable deployments.

Some of the features that the API Management Exposure should support include:

- Discovery of API, extended to dynamic and volatile resources and functions.
- Registration and release of APIs, for both internal and third-party functions. This action can be handled as part of the LCM of the function exposing the API.
- Routing across multiple API providers or related function instances, including failover management and load balancing.
- Access control, with management of access policies, authentication, and authorization of API consumers. For the cases where API consumers are from external administrative domains, federation should be supported.
- Traceability of every request-response message exchanged between API providers and invokers, to allow auditability and further applications enabled by it.

API Gateways

As previously mentioned, the exposure of capabilities through APIs requires a series of features from the point of view of the use of the API (Discovery, Routing, Access Control, Logging, etc.) that are usually implemented by what is called API Gateways.

Below we will describe the proposal of this API Gateway for 3GPP and what solutions, mainly open source, exist that can offer this functionality.

3GPP CAPIF

3GPP has defined the architecture and characteristics that the API Gateway must have in what it has called CAPIF (Common API Framework for 3GPP Northbound APIs). The functional model of CAPIF is represented in the following figure:

Source: 3GPP

Figure 10 3GPP CAPIF framework

CAPIF framework consists of four main modules:

CAPIF Core Function (CCF), responsible for applying access control to the external applications, while keeping track of their service API invocations.

API Exposure Function (AEF), which provides the endpoints of service APIs, authorizes the API invocations, and records them in log files.

API Publishing Function (APF), responsible for the publication of service APIs to CCF, to make them discoverable to the invokers.

API Management Function (AMF), auditing service API invocation logs and managing the on-/off-boarding of applications into operator's system.

In this paper³¹ CAPIF is proposed as the reference API GW for CAMARA. The reason for this proposal is twofold. On the one hand, CAPIF is a normative solution with wide acceptance at industry. The other main advantage of CAPIF is that though specified by the 3GPP, it is not tied to 3GPP APIs; indeed, CAPIF can be used as an API Gateway for any API, regardless of their semantics. Therefore, it is an ideal candidate to publish CAMARA APIs, and policy their exposure to the 3rd party applications. A generic workflow for Service API Invocation is depicted:

³¹ J Ordonez-Lucena and Felix Dsouza, "Pathways towards Network-as-a-Service: the CAMARA Project", 2022 Workshop on Network-Application Integration (NAI '22), August 22, 2022, Amsterdam, Netherlands

Source: Workshop on Network-Application Integration (NAI '22)

Figure 11 CAPIF Generic workflow for service API invocation

In EVOLVED-5G project, the CAPIF framework is developed to provide NetApp developers with the appropriate API calls to realize the communication between the NetApp and the 5GC. A dummy NetApp has been developed to serve as the basis and example for all NetApp developers, with a proper implementation of NEF and CAPIF API calls, in order to let the NetApp interoperation with the 5G network be automatically tested.

*Red Hat 3scale*³²

In the commercial world Red Hat proposes its API Gateway 3scale as an implementation of CAPIF. 3scale is made up of two modules, API Manager and API Gateway, as shown in the following figure:

³² <https://www.3scale.net/>

Source: Red Hat

Figure 12 Red Hat 3scale architecture

3Scale **API Manager** acts as CAPIF Core Function, API publishing and API management function. **API Gateway** act as API Exposing function.

Open source API Gateways

In the open source world, there are numerous initiatives for generic API Gateways that can be used as the basis for building the framework proposed in CAPIF. The most relevant initiatives are the following.

Kong³³

Kong is an open source API gateway that is built on top of NGINX, which is a very popular open source HTTP proxy server. Even though Kong is open source, KongHQ³⁴ provides maintenance and support licenses for large enterprise. While basic features are had with the open-source version, certain features like the Admin UI, Security, and developer portal are available only with an enterprise license.

³³ <https://github.com/Kong/kong>

³⁴ <https://konghq.com/products/kong-gateway>

Kong out of box provides many expected features of API Management, such as creating API keys, Routing to multiple microservices, etc. It doesn't have a lot of transformation layer (mostly HTTP based transformation, no SOAP or to XML). Even though it comes with rate limiting, it doesn't have billing integrations. The administration and management task can be performed via CLI or curl commands to a REST API which makes management easier to integrate within your existing devops playbooks.

Tyk.io³⁵

Like Kong, Tyk is also open source, but it is under MPL license, which is less permissive than Kong's Apache 2.0 license. At the same time, Tyk's enterprise user uses exactly the same gateway as a community user. You don't have to pay extra for certain enterprise features.

Tyk has features such as Key Management, Quotas, Rate Limit, API version, access control, but no integrated billing features. Tyk has both a REST API and a web dashboard to do administrative tasks. While they do have an extension list, Tyk doesn't have as large of a community or the plugin hub that Kong has. However, they do keep their gateway well designed and attempt to keep it lean.

KrakenD³⁶

KrakenD is an extensible, declarative, high-performance open-source API Gateway. Its core functionality is to create an API that acts as an aggregator of many microservices into single endpoints, doing the heavy-lifting automatically for you: aggregate, transform, filter, decode, throttle, auth, and more.

KrakenD needs no programming as it offers a declarative way to create the endpoints. It is well structured and layered, and open to extending its functionality using plug-and-play middleware developed by the community or in-house. KrakenD focuses on being a pure Layer 7 API gateway, not coupled to the HTTP transport layer.

Apache APISIX³⁷

Developed and donated by API7.ai, Apache APISIX is an open source, dynamic, scalable, and high-performance cloud native API gateway for all your APIs and microservices. It is a top-level project of the Apache Software Foundation.

You can use APISIX API Gateway as a traffic entrance to process all business data. It offers features including dynamic routing, dynamic upstream, dynamic certificates, A/B testing, canary release, blue-green deployment, limit rate, defense against malicious attacks, metrics, monitoring alarms, service observability, service governance, and more.

8.3.2 Innovation in 6GSMART-ICC

The previous section has surveyed existing solutions for exposing capability beyond the boundaries of one single administrative domain. These solutions, which include architecture and API Gateway solutions, coincide on the need to define mediation layers to policy the interaction between consumer and provider domain. However, neither of

³⁵ <https://tyk.io/>

³⁶ <https://www.krakend.io/>

³⁷ <https://apisix.apache.org/>

them focuses on the particularities that industry 4.0 scenarios pose in the IoT-edge-cloud continuum, with industry service resources (network, cloud, applications) deployed across multiple provider domains, each potentially operated by a different stakeholder. Examples of these provider domains include:

- **Factory infrastructure**, owned by the OT enterprises. Though most OT enterprises prefer to operate the private network infrastructures themselves, not all of them have skilled workforce; in such a case, they can outsource the operational activities to a managed service provider. Examples of these managed service providers are i) the business units of MNOs; ii) the business units of telco vendors; iii) solution providers specialized in private networking.
- **Public cloud nodes**, owned and operated by large-scale cloud providers, i.e. hyperscalers.
- **Public network**, owned and operated by the local units of MNOs.

In this taxonomy, it is assumed that:

- The OT enterprise has the contract signed with one single MNO. This is the typical situation for private LTE/5G, and it is expected to remain the main trend in the coming years.
- Some of the network resources providing device-to-application connectivity are provided by the public network, in form of a slice. Actually, slicing is a provisioning solution for PNI-NPN (see Figure 5).
- The ownership of network resources is decoupled from their hosting/location. In fact, some of the private network resources (i.e., industrial analytics function) can be hosted in the public network domain, while some of the public network resources (i.e., Core's subscriber data management) can be deployed in the factory premises.

This has an impact on the discovery of resources and capabilities, and their programmatic consumption through APIs, considering the OT enterprises are provided with a single-entry point for the management and supervision of their services.

Gap: The OT enterprise needs to be provided with a single-entry point to manage service, even for the cases where the service resources spanned across the IoT-edge-cloud continuum, with different provider domains in between. This has an impact on the discovery of resources, and their programmatic consumption through APIs, in a consistent way.

Action plan: 6G-SMART-ICC aims to bridge this gap, by crafting a mediation solution that provides OT enterprises with consistent yet resilient access to service capabilities in distributed environments. This mediation solution will be materialized in an API GW solution featuring:

- Dynamic discovery of resources, with the ability of provider domains to announce their managed resources and inform of their status and capabilities in real-time. Focus on resource volatility for the extreme-edge.
- Improved network rate distribution and control.
- Better visibility for monitoring and fault management, that the OT enterprise can use for the SLA management.
- An additional safety layer for DDoS attack. The API gateway using policies can stop irregular behavior, directed towards one/many services.
- Clear view on key metrics and logs related to communication flow passing through the gateway, that enables early fault detection.

9 Preliminary System Architecture

9.1 System Requirements [TID, MINSAIT, ATOS]

ID	Requirements
6GSMART-ICC.R01	The system managed resources include cloud infrastructure and network resources. For network resources, 5G, WiFi and TSN technologies are considered.
6GSMART-ICC.R01	The system managed resources can be distributed across the IoT-edge-cloud continuum, spanning different provider domains in between (i.e., factory premises, public network, public cloud nodes).
6GSMART-ICC.R02	The system represents an NPN, where the OT enterprise acts as NPN customer and the NPN operator is played by the operator of constituent provider domains.
6GSMART-ICC.R03	There shall be a "separation of concerns" of the NPN operator and the NPN customer, meaning that the customer and operator do not require knowledge of each other's internal workings and implementation details
6GSMART-ICC.R04	The system use cases shall support SNPN (resources not provided by the public network) and PNI-NPN scenarios (include resources provided by the public network).
6GSMART-ICC.R05	The system shall provide a unified Northbound Interface (NBI) for NPN customer to interact with the system. This NBI shall rely on dev-friendly APIs.
6GSMART-ICC.R06	The system shall have Southbound Interfaces (SBIs) to interact with the different provider domains.
6GSMART-ICC.R07	The SBI that allow the system to interact with the MNO shall be aligned with the GSMA Open Gateway initiative.
6GSMART-ICC.R08	<p>The system shall allow an industry application to be deployed where it can utilize the optimum resources, as long as these resources are within the logical perimeter of the NPN operator.</p> <p>NOTE: For SNPN scenarios, this perimeter does not include public network resources.</p>
6GSMART-ICC.R09	The system shall support applications packaged as VMs or containers.
6GSMART-ICC.R10	Applications processes running in containers and VMs, and their data, shall be protected. Approaches to protecting them include process isolation via name-spacing or hypervisor controls and trusted enclaves.
6GSMART-ICC.R11	The system shall apply protection mechanisms to ensure service availability to prevent attacks targeting the availability of exposed applications/services, e.g., denial of service attacks and brute force attacks
6GSMART-ICC.R12	The system shall provide the NPN customer with tools and experience similar what is available today in public cloud environments, to facilitate the portability of applications from the public cloud to industrial edge cloud.
6GSMART-ICC.R13	The system shall allow the NPN customer to onboard/offload applications.

6GSMART-ICC.R14	The system shall allow the NPN customer to discover the resources on which industrial applications can be deployed for use by end-user devices. These resources shall be within the logical perimeter of the NPN operator.
6GSMART-ICC.R15	The system shall allow the NPN customer to reserve resources for future application instances deployments, ensuring the availability of the booked capacity
6GSMART-ICC.R16	The system shall allow the NPN customer to issue orders for the deployment of application instances, according to a set of input requirements.
6GSMART-ICC.R17	The system shall allow a deployed application to consume control, configuration and management capabilities through the NBI, using industry-tailored user-friendly APIs.
6GSMART-ICC.R18	The system shall allow a deployed industrial application store data in a manner that is secure and compliant with applicable local regulations.
6GSMART-ICC.R19	The system shall allow application subscribers (mobile users) accessing edge resources to move locations within or outside the factory, and they can do so while using the service.
6GSMART-ICC.R20	The system shall offer the NPN customer the ability to restrict where the industrial application is deployed to meet Data Protection requirements. NOTE: Data protection regulations differ between countries and regions (such as the EU).
6GSMART-ICC.R21	The system shall be able to serve the Data Protection needs of the NPN customer, by protecting data beyond regulatory requirements
6GSMART-ICC.R22	The system shall allow the NPN customer to restrict the service footprint of one industrial application to devices in particular geographic areas
6GSMART-ICC.R23	The system shall allow the NPN customer to require that outbound access to the internet is prohibited.

9.2 High-Level Design [TID, MINSAIT, ATOS]

The solution proposed is a cloud continuum management platform that securely deploys industrial distributed applications on devices, premises, telco edge and public environments.

Normally a distributed application is broken down into components that are usually groups of microservices deployed in a Kubernetes cluster. These components communicate with each other and with the end user to provide a service. There is a clear trend to take more and more components of these applications to the cloud, but nevertheless there are cases in which for different reasons (for example, need for low latency) the components cannot be taken to the cloud, but instead that have to be located closer to the end user. To meet these requirements, operators offer through

APIs what they have called NaaS (Network as Service) such as the GSMA initiative called Open Gateway.

Through these APIs, operators mainly offer:

- Computing and storage capacity.
- Network connectivity with particular characteristics, normally through slices.
- Information and control of the connectivity of the different devices to the networks (QoS, Location, etc.).

Figure 13 shows how the orchestrator uses two of the previous APIs in the interfaces that we have called SBI-Cloud (computing and storage) and SBI-NW (connectivity with particular characteristics). On the other hand, applications can also request services from the network (information and connectivity control) through the interface that we have called NW APIs.

Figure 13 Solution Architecture

The main components to be developed are the orchestrator (CORC) and the Network APIs.

CORC

<ATOS corc description>

Network APIs

In this project, we are going to test the CAMARA QoD API (or similar) with a network aware application. To do so, we are going to select the API Gateway and develop the corresponding transformation function following the GSAM Open Gateway Architecture.

Source: GSMA

Figure 14 GSAM Open Gateway

10 Summary and conclusions

As enterprises continue supporting wider digitization, the demands on secure and reliable connectivity solutions are increasing. Advanced connectivity is an essential element for industrial automation applications in manufacturing facilities, Automotive, Hospitals, and Warehousing Facilities.

5G-ACIA, the main driver for the development of private 5G solutions in industry 4.0 ecosystem, has defined several use case families that goes from factory automation to monitoring and maintenance. These use cases have different service requirements that in some cases are very strict and require latencies of less than 1ms.

Different enablers such as 5G, Wifi, TSN and Edge Computing offer the necessary solutions to provide the required connectivity. Mobile operators are developing 5G networks at high speed and could offer complete solutions to companies, but nevertheless, for different reasons such as privacy, different deployment scenarios are valued, ranging from PNI-NPN networks to SNPN networks.

Edge computing and 5G service/connectivity provisioning capabilities (e.g., slicing) are not considered within the 5G-ACIA exposure landscape. However, these capabilities are presumed to play a key role for industry 4.0 service innovation and new business models. 6G-SMART-ICC aims define which capabilities related to edge computing and

5G service/connectivity provisioning makes sense to expose to industrial applications and push these capabilities for their adoption into GSMA Open Gateway initiative, to promote their adoption at large scale.

On the other hand, current APIs to expose network capabilities (NaaS) to industrial applications are studied. Organizations such as 3GPP and CAMARA have defined Capability Exposure APIs. 3GPP exposure APIs cannot be directly exposed to industrial applications, since their semantics convey low-level parameters that are quite complex for OT companies to understand (and thus configure/monitor). And CAMARA seems a more appropriate target, though today's focus is on mass-market, whose SLS expectations are quite far from the ones inherent to industry 4.0 services. 6G-SMART-ICC is going to identify which CAMARA APIs can remain valid for industry 4.0 services, and how they need to be enriched to cope with the specificities of these services.

Finally, the exposure of capabilities between different domains is studied with special emphasis on the API Gateway, reaching the conclusion that the OT enterprise needs to be provided with a single-entry point to manage service, even for the cases where the service resources spanned across the IoT-edge-cloud continuum, with different provider domains in between. This has an impact on the discovery of resources, and their programmatic consumption through APIs, in a consistent way.

6G-SMART-ICC aims to bridge this gap, by crafting a mediation solution that provides OT enterprises with consistent yet resilient access to service capabilities in distributed environments. This mediation solution will be materialized in an API GW solution featuring:

- Dynamic discovery of resources, with the ability of provider domains to announce their managed resources and inform of their status and capabilities in real-time. Focus on resource volatility for the extreme-edge.
- Improved network rate distribution and control.
- Better visibility for monitoring and fault management, that the OT enterprise can use for the SLA management.
- An additional safety layer for DDoS attack. The API gateway using policies can stop irregular behavior, directed towards one/many services.
- Clear view on key metrics and logs related to communication flow passing through the gateway, that enables early fault detection.